

STRATEGIC ADAPTATION IN THE MODERN ERA: LEVERAGING INTERNAL AUDITOR FOR ENHANCED RISK MANAGEMENT IN ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE

Antonette Recodig Ranara, Erwin Babaran Quendangan, MBA, PhD

School of Graduate Studies, AMA University, Quezon City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

In today's rapidly evolving business environment, marked by technological advancements and dynamic market conditions, organizations must continually adapt to remain competitive and sustainable. This study investigates the crucial role of internal auditors in facilitating strategic adaptation through enhanced risk management during organizational change. By leveraging their unique skills and capabilities, internal auditors can effectively identify, assess, and mitigate risks associated with strategic transformations. The research employed a quantitative approach with a Likert scale design to evaluate internal auditors' contributions, assess the effectiveness of to enhance their capabilities, and identify factors influencing strategic adaptation. A sample of 101 internal auditors, selected using stratified sampling, participated in the study. Data collection involved structured questionnaires, unstructured interviews, and online research, with a pilot test conducted for refinement. Accurate statistical methods provided robust conclusions and informed recommendations. Results indicated that respondents strongly agreed on the high effectiveness of internal auditors in risk management, enhancing Kotter's 8 steps in organizational change. Key components on Training and Professional Development, Utilization of Related Technology, Collaboration and Communication, and Regular Risk Assessment and Feedback Mechanisms were rated as extremely effective, giving management flexible and affordable implementation options. Additionally, factors influencing the need for strategic adaptation were found to have a very high overall influence, highlighting the necessity of prioritizing these efforts to maintain effective risk management in the face of technological advancements and organizational change. Implementing the recommendations will help organizations

establish a solid foundation for effective risk management, strategic adaptation, and sustainable growth. Although the exact relationship between internal factors and risk identification components may be uncertain, improving these areas will enhance organizational resilience and readiness for future challenges.

Keywords: *Modern Era, Internal Auditor, Risk Management, Organizational Change, Technological Advancement*

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary business environment, characterized by rapid technological advancements and dynamic market conditions, organizations face increasing pressure to adapt and innovate to maintain competitiveness and sustainability. This study, investigates the pivotal role of internal auditors in facilitating strategic adaptation during organizational change. By examining how internal auditors can enhance risk management practices, this research aims to address significant gaps in the current literature and provide actionable insights for organizations navigating technological transformations.

Technological advancements such as artificial intelligence, automation, and digital platforms have profound implications for organizational structures, processes, and cultures (Smith & Johnson, 2023). These innovations necessitate comprehensive risk management strategies to mitigate potential disruptions and leverage new opportunities. Internal auditors, traditionally seen as guardians of financial integrity, are increasingly recognized for their strategic role in assessing and managing risks associated with technological change (Garcia & Thompson, 2024). However, there remains a gap in understanding the specific contributions of internal auditors in the context of organizational change driven by technological advancements.

The impact of technological advancements on organizational change management is well-documented. Smith and Johnson (2023) highlight the challenges and opportunities posed by emerging technologies, emphasizing the need for effective change management strategies. Generational dynamics further complicate this landscape, as different cohorts perceive and respond to change differently (Chen & Davis, 2022). Leadership plays a crucial role in guiding organizations through digital transformations, with effective communication and collaboration being key (Garcia & Thompson, 2024). Risk management practices are also evolving in response to technological advancements. Wang and Smith (2023) explore how technologies like artificial intelligence and blockchain influence risk management during organizational change, underscoring the need for adaptive strategies. Additionally, Lee and Johnson (2022) examine how generational dynamics impact risk perception and management, highlighting the importance of tailored communication strategies. Internal auditors are at the forefront of these changes, adapting their roles to address new challenges. Zhang and Patel (2023) investigate how internal auditors navigate technological advancements

and generational dynamics, while Wang and Lee (2022) explore the integration of technology in internal audit practices. These studies suggest that internal auditors' expertise in risk assessment and their ability to leverage technology are crucial for effective risk management in the modern era.

Despite the extensive research on technological advancements and risk management, there is a notable gap in understanding how internal auditors specifically contribute to strategic adaptation during organizational change. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the enhanced role of internal auditors in managing risks associated with technological transformations. The timeliness of this topic is underscored by the ongoing digital revolution and the need for organizations to remain agile and resilient.

By focusing on the strategic integration of internal audit practices with organizational change initiatives, this research proposes an innovative framework that leverages internal auditors' capabilities to support and enhance Kotter's 8 steps for successful organizational change. The study's findings will provide practical insights and recommendations for organizations seeking to improve their risk management practices during periods of technological change. Recent literature refines Kotter's influential model for organizational change, highlighting the importance of data-driven urgency (Reissner, 2021), diverse coalitions for risk mitigation (Mantere & Vaara, 2020), agile strategies (Kotter & Scharmer, 2020), advanced communication (Gandz, 2022), digital empowerment (Fleming & Spicer, 2020), rapid experimentation for quick wins (Jones & Linder, 2021), embedding risk management in culture (Champoux & Peters, 2020), and fostering innovation and risk-taking (Bouckenooghe et al., 2023). However, there is a significant research gap regarding the role of internal auditors in identifying, assessing, and mitigating risks at each step of Kotter's model. This study is timely and relevant due to the rapid pace of technological advancements and complex organizational environments, aiming to enhance internal auditors' capabilities in strategic adaptation and risk management, thus ensuring organizational resilience and competitiveness.

In conclusion, this research contributes to the existing body of knowledge by addressing a significant gap in the literature, offering timely and relevant insights, and proposing a new approach to leveraging internal auditors for enhanced risk management in organizational change.

Research Questions

In this study, the focus is on exploring and enhancing the role of internal auditors in managing risks and supporting strategic adaptation during organizational change. Rather than framing the research around primary and sub-questions, the study adopts a set of research objectives to comprehensively address the various dimensions of this topic. The objectives provide a structured approach to investigate the capabilities of internal auditors, the influence of technological advancements, and the internal factors affecting strategic adaptation. This objective-driven approach allows for a thorough examination of the complexities involved, enabling a more detailed and actionable understanding of how internal auditors can optimize their contributions in dynamic business environments.

To explore how internal auditors can enhance risk management during organizational change by leveraging technological advancements and strategic adaptation.

1. To determine the demographic profile of internal auditors, including age, years of experience as auditor, and gender, and examine how these factors might affect their effectiveness in risk management.
2. To evaluate the contributions of internal auditors in identifying, assessing, and mitigating risks during organizational change, and assess the impact of technological advancements on these contributions.
3. To identify the capabilities of internal auditors that need strengthening in the context of:
 - Training and professional development
 - Utilization of technology
 - Collaboration and communication
 - Regular risk assessment and feedback mechanisms
4. To determine the internal factors influencing the need for strategic adaptation during organizational change, such as:
 - Workplace environment
 - Skills assessment
 - Leadership alignment
 - Technological advancement
 - Change management
5. To investigate the relationship between risk identification components and internal factors influencing strategic adaptation.
6. To apply research findings to develop or enhance a framework that aligns the role of internal auditors with organizational change and strategic adaptation in the modern era

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in various organizations across different industries, focusing on those undergoing significant organizational change due to technological advancements. Specific details regarding the institutions involved are withheld to maintain confidentiality. Stratified sampling was employed to ensure representation across different organizational roles within the internal audit function. This method helps in capturing diverse perspectives and experiences relevant to the study. The respondents consisted of 101 internal auditors selected through the sampling process. They varied in terms of age, gender, years of experience, and organizational roles. Demographic data were collected to understand how these factors might influence perceptions and practices related to risk management during organizational change. Data were collected using structured surveys questionnaires supplemented by unstructured interviews. The survey instrument included items designed to assess the effectiveness and of the of internal auditors in managing risks associated with organizational change, and internal factors influencing the need for strategic adaptation. The questionnaire utilized a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree." Prior to full implementation, a pilot test was conducted with 21 internal auditors to refine the questionnaire for clarity and coherence. The survey instrument comprised 30 items addressing various aspects of internal auditors' roles and capabilities in risk management during organizational change. The questionnaire was researcher-designed based on a comprehensive review of relevant literature and prior research. It aimed to capture perceptions on internal auditors' effectiveness, the impact of technological advancements, and strategies for enhancing risk management practices. Quantitative data analysis involved descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, weighted mean, and standard deviation, to summarize survey responses, data distribution, provides an average considering varying importance, measures data spread, and gauges overall sentiment or consensus and correlation analysis to explore relationships between variables.

The scope of the study focused on the internal auditors' contributions to risk management in the context of organizational change driven by technological advancements. Limitations included potential response bias in self-reported data and the generalizability of findings beyond the sampled organizations. The study did not address specific proprietary information or disclose identifiable details of participating institutions due to confidentiality agreements.

RESULTS

Figure 1: Respondents as to Gender

Gender	<i>f</i>	%	<i>Rank</i>
Male	47	47%	2
Female	50	50%	1
LGBTQ	3	3%	3
Prefer not to disclose	1	1%	4
Total	101		

Figure 2: Respondents as to Age

Age Range	f	%	Rank
20 below	0	0%	8
20 to 25	2	2%	7
26 to 30	12	12%	6
31 to 35	18	18%	3
36 to 40	14	14%	5
41 to 45	21	21%	1
46 to 50	19	19%	2
Above 50	15	15%	4
Total	101		

Figure 3: Respondents as to Year of Experience as Auditor

Age Range	f	%	Rank
Less than 1 year	0	0%	5
1 to 3 years	6	6%	4
4 to 6 years	14	14%	3
7 to 9 years	28	28%	2
More than 10 years	53	52%	1

Figure 4: Internal Auditors Contribution

Internal Audit Contribution	Mean	Standard Deviation	Net Agreement Rating
Risk Identification	4.91	0.31776	99.01
Risk Assessment	4.97	0.169767	100.00
Risk Mitigation	4.96	0.195027	100.00
Providing recommendations	4.97	0.169767	100.00
Collaborating with stakeholders	4.95	0.258566	99.01

Figure 5: The effectiveness of the following components to strengthen the capabilities of the internal auditors in identifying, assessing and mitigating risk

1. Training and Professional Development	Mean	Net Agreement Rating	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
A. Organizational Culture	4.99	100.00	Extremely Effective	1
B. Flexibility and Agility	4.95	100.00	Very Effective	4
C. Employee Empowerment and Engagement	4.98	100.00	Extremely Effective	2

D. Employee Skills and Training	4.99	100.00	Extremely Effective	1
E. Physical workspace design and layout	4.96	99.01	Very Effective	3
2. Utilization of Related Technology				
A. Data Analytics and Business Intelligence Tools	4.99	100.00	Extremely Effective	1
B. Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML)	4.95	99.01	Very Effective	3
C. Robotic Process Automation (RPA)	4.95	99.01	Very Effective	3
D. Blockchain Technology	4.97	100.00	Extremely Effective	2
E. Cybersecurity Tools and Technologies	4.97	100.00	Extremely Effective	2
3. Collaboration and Communication				
A. Regular Team Meetings	4.97	100.00	Extremely Effective	3
B. Collaboration and Communication Platforms	4.99	100.00	Extremely Effective	1
C. Brainstorming and Problem-Solving	4.98	100.00	Extremely Effective	2
D. Knowledge Sharing Platforms	4.95	100.00	Extremely Effective	4
E. Survey and Polling Tools	4.94	99.01	Very Effective	5
4. Regular Risk Assessment and Mitigation				
A. Comprehensive Risk Identification	4.97	100.00	Extremely Effective	2
B. Scenario Planning and Sensitivity Analysis	4.97	100.00	Extremely Effective	2
C. Risk Quantification	4.97	99.01	Very Effective	3
D. Continuous Improvement	4.98	100.00	Extremely Effective	1
E. Integration of Technology in Audit Procedures	4.97	100.00	Extremely Effective	2
5. Feedback Mechanism				
A. Open Communication Channels	4.98	100.00	Extremely Effective	1
B. Peer Reviews and Knowledge Sharing	4.96	100.00	Extremely Effective	3

C. 360-Degree Feedback	4.97	100.00	Extremely Effective	2
D. Performance Metrics and Key Performance Indicators	4.94	99.01	Very Effective	4
E. Feedback Integration into Audit Processes	4.93	99.01	Very Effective	5

Figure 6: Internal factors influencing the need for strategic adaptation in the workstation.

1. Workplace Environment	Mean	Net Agreement Rating	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
A. Organizational Culture	4.90	98.02	High Influence	5
B. Flexibility and Agility	4.96	99.01	High Influence	3
C. Employee Empowerment and Engagement	4.95	99.01	High Influence	4
D. Employee Skills and Training	4.97	100.00	Very High Influence	1
E. Physical workspace design and layout	4.84	100.00	Very High Influence	2
2. Skill Assessment				
A. Innovations and Creativity	4.89	100.00	Very High Influence	3
B. Skills gap analysis	4.97	100.00	Very High Influence	1
C. Technology Literacy	4.97	99.01	High Influence	4
D. Recruitment and talent acquisition strategies	4.79	95.05	High Influence	5
E. Diversity and Inclusion	4.90	100.00	Very High Influence	2
3. Leadership Alignment				
A. Vision and direction	4.99	100.00	Very High Influence	1
B. Understanding of Technology Trends	4.97	100.00	Very High Influence	2
C. Commitment to Innovation	4.98	99.01	High Influence	4
D. Alignment of leadership styles with organizational culture	4.84	99.01	High Influence	5
E. Resource Allocation	4.86	100.00	Very High Influence	3
4. Technological Advancement				

A. Integration of new technologies into business processes	4.91	100.00	Very High Influence	1
B. Pace of Change	4.81	99.01	High Influence	5
C. Cybersecurity Risk	4.90	100.00	Very High Influence	2
D. Ethical and Social Implication	4.85	99.01	High Influence	4
E. Disruptive Innovation	4.90	99.01	High Influence	3
5. Change Management				
A. Change readiness assessment	4.89	98.02	High Influence	3
B. Stakeholder engagement strategies	4.89	97.03	High Influence	5
C. Training and Skill Development	4.89	98.02	Very High Influence	4
D. Culture and Behavior Change	4.89	99.01	High Influence	2
E. Continuous improvement and feedback loops	4.97	100.00	Very High Influence	1

Figure 7: Significant relationship between the components of identifying risk in the organizational change and the internal factors that influence the need for strategic adaptation.

Internal Factors	Mean	Rank	Components	Mean	Rank	D1	D ²
Workplace Environment	4.92	2	Training and Professional Development	4.97	2.5	0.5	0.25
Skills Assessment	4.9	4	Utilization of Related Technology	4.97	2.5	1.5	2.25
Leadership Alignment	4.93	1	Collaboration and Communication	4.97	2.5	1.5	2.25
Technological Advancement	4.88	5	Regular Risk Assessment and Mitigation	4.97	2.5	2.5	6.25
Change Management	4.91	3	Feedback Mechanism	4.96	5	2	4
						Total	15

Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient(rs)	Alpha, Significance Level (α)	Degrees of Freedom (df)	T-Statistic (t)
1.25	0.05	3	0.4472

DISCUSSION

The data on figure number 4 regarding the contribution of internal auditor reveals a highly positive perception of internal audits' contributions to risk management, with respondents overwhelmingly agreeing on their significant role in risk identification, assessment, mitigation, and providing recommendations. The low standard deviation indicates a strong consensus among respondents, reinforcing the positive feedback. With net agreement ratings reaching 100% for key areas, there is near-universal endorsement of internal audits' effectiveness. This strong agreement underscores internal audits' critical role in enhancing risk management and stakeholder collaboration during organizational change, particularly in the context of technological advancement.

The data on figure number 5 regarding the effectiveness of the components to strengthen the capabilities of the internal auditors in identifying, assessing and mitigating risk associated with organizational change considering technological advancement evaluates various components essential for enhancing the capabilities of internal auditors in managing risks associated with organizational change, especially in the context of technological advancements. It covers training and professional development, technological tools, collaboration and communication, and feedback mechanisms.

Organizational culture and continuous employee training are identified as the most effective components in strengthening internal auditors' capabilities. A strong organizational culture fosters an environment where auditors feel supported and aligned with company values, crucial for managing risks during technological changes. Similarly, continuous training equips auditors with up-to-date skills to handle evolving risks effectively. Empowering and engaging employees also plays a significant role by making auditors more proactive and adept at applying their knowledge to risk management. Although slightly less critical, the design of physical workspaces enhances productivity and collaboration, supporting auditors' ability to manage risks.

Technological tools are crucial in supporting internal auditors. Data analytics and business intelligence tools are rated as the most effective, enabling efficient processing and analysis of large data volumes to identify risks and trends. Blockchain technology and cybersecurity tools are also highly effective, providing transparency, security, and protection against cyber threats. AI and ML technologies are valued for their advanced analytical capabilities, while Robotic Process Automation (RPA) is recognized for automating repetitive tasks, allowing auditors to focus on more complex risk management activities.

Collaboration and communication are fundamental to effective internal auditing. Collaboration platforms, brainstorming sessions, and regular team meetings are deemed extremely effective in facilitating seamless interaction and collective problem-solving. Knowledge sharing platforms also play a crucial role in continuous learning and adapting to technological changes. Survey and polling tools, while slightly less critical, contribute significantly to understanding stakeholder feedback and enhancing communication within the audit process.

Continuous improvement is rated as the most effective, ensuring that risk management processes are regularly reviewed and enhanced. Comprehensive risk identification is crucial for detecting all potential risks, providing a solid foundation for subsequent efforts. Scenario planning and sensitivity analysis help auditors prepare for various contingencies, enhancing their ability to manage risks. Integrating technology into audit procedures and risk quantification are also vital, enabling more efficient risk assessment and prioritization.

Feedback mechanisms are vital for continuous improvement in internal auditing. Open communication channels are the most effective, fostering transparent dialogue and timely feedback. Peer reviews and knowledge sharing are also highly effective, encouraging collaborative learning and refinement of risk management techniques. The 360-degree feedback mechanism provides a comprehensive view of an auditor's performance, while performance metrics and KPIs, though slightly less impactful, are essential for setting standards and monitoring progress. Integrating feedback into audit processes is crucial for implementing improvements based on feedback.

Overall, the high ratings across all components reflect strong agreement on their effectiveness in enhancing internal auditors' capabilities. The emphasis on organizational culture, training, and employee engagement underscores their importance in managing risks associated with technological advancements. Technological tools, effective collaboration and communication, and robust feedback mechanisms are all crucial for supporting auditors in adapting to and mitigating risks in a rapidly changing environment.

The data on figure number 6 regarding Internal factors influencing the need for strategic adaptation in the workstation evaluates the influence of various components of the workplace environment, skill assessment, leadership alignment, technological advancement, and change management in influencing the need for strategic adaptation in the workstation. Each component is assessed based on mean scores, net agreement ratings, and verbal interpretations, with employee skills and training being highlighted as the most effective workplace environment component. Continuous skill development programs equip employees with the knowledge and competencies required to navigate technological advancements, emphasizing the importance of investing in employee development to manage risks associated with organizational change effectively.

Skill assessment identifies and leverages internal auditors' capabilities, particularly during organizational change and technological advancements. Skills gap analysis is crucial for determining specific skills and competencies lacking within the organization,

enabling the development of targeted training programs. Diversity and inclusion bring varied perspectives and innovative ideas critical for effective risk management and problem-solving. Encouraging innovation and creativity within the organization supports strategic adaptation, while technology literacy ensures employees can effectively use new technologies. Recruitment strategies, although rated lower, remain influential for building an adaptable workforce.

Leadership alignment is critical for guiding organizations through change and ensuring successful strategic adaptations, especially with technological advancements. Clear vision and direction from leadership are essential, alongside a deep understanding of technology trends to inform decision-making. Effective resource allocation supports strategic initiatives, and a commitment to innovation drives the development of new solutions to manage technological risks. Aligning leadership styles with organizational culture facilitates smoother transitions and greater acceptance of changes.

Technological advancement significantly drives organizational change, with the integration of new technologies into business processes being the most influential component. Effective integration enhances efficiency and productivity, ensuring competitiveness and minimal disruption. Cybersecurity risk is crucial due to increased threats from new technologies, requiring robust measures to protect assets and maintain trust. Disruptive innovation challenges existing business models, necessitating quick adaptation. Ethical and social implications must be considered for positive reputation and compliance, while the rapid pace of technological change requires agile and responsive strategies.

Effective change management is essential for navigating organizational change complexities, particularly with technological advancements. Continuous improvement and feedback loops are the most influential components, emphasizing ongoing evaluation and process enhancement. A supportive organizational culture and adaptive behavior are critical for fostering an environment that embraces change, mitigating resistance, and promoting smooth transitions. Assessing change readiness evaluates an organization's capacity to handle change, identifying potential barriers and areas needing support. Well-designed training programs enhance employee competency and confidence, facilitating adaptation to new challenges.

Engaging stakeholders is crucial for successful change management, involving them in the change process to build support, address concerns, and consider all relevant insights. Effective stakeholder engagement, while slightly lower in ranking, remains essential for comprehensive change management. Overall, these components collectively influence the need for strategic adaptation in the workstation, ensuring organizations effectively manage risks associated with organizational change and technological advancements.

The data on figure number 6, The calculated t-value (0.4472) is compared to the critical t-value from the t-distribution table at $df=3$ $df =$ and $\alpha=0.05$. The critical value for a two-tailed test with $df = 3$ at $\alpha=0.05$ is approximately 3.182. Since the calculated t-value

(0.4472) is less than the critical value, it indicates that the correlation is not statistically significant to conclude that there is a relationship between internal factors influencing strategic adaptation and components of identifying risk.

Conclusions

The study conclusively demonstrates that internal auditors play an indispensable role in safeguarding organizations against risks during periods of change. Their ability to adapt and leverage modern tools and practices positions them as key contributors to organizational resilience and success in the dynamic business landscape of the modern era. The extremely positive feedback from respondents affirms the importance of these strategies, providing a clear roadmap for enhancing risk management through effective internal auditing practices. Ultimately, it is up to the management to decide which measures are most applicable and affordable for their organization, ensuring that risk management practices are tailored to their specific needs and constraints.

By implementing the recommendations, organizations can build a robust foundation for effective risk management, strategic adaptation, and sustainable growth. While the specific relationship between internal factors and risk identification components may not be definite, strategic improvements in these areas can collectively strengthen organizational resilience and readiness for future challenges. Continual evaluation and adaptation of strategies will be essential in maintaining competitive advantage and achieving long-term success

Recommendations

To enhance the capabilities of internal auditors in managing risks associated with technological advancements, organizations should focus on cultivating a strong organizational culture and investing in continuous training programs that emphasize the latest technological trends and risk management techniques. Employee engagement should be enhanced through initiatives that empower and motivate auditors to proactively contribute to risk management. Additionally, prioritizing the integration of advanced data analytics, business intelligence tools, blockchain, and cybersecurity technologies will improve data processing, transparency, and security. Leveraging AI, machine learning, and RPA can further enhance predictive analytics and automate routine tasks, allowing auditors to concentrate on strategic risk management. Promoting collaboration and communication through robust platforms, regular brainstorming sessions, team meetings, and knowledge-sharing initiatives will foster innovative thinking and problem-solving. Finally, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and implementing transparent feedback mechanisms, including 360-degree feedback and peer reviews, will ensure auditors are continuously developing and adapting to new challenges. By implementing

these strategies, organizations can significantly strengthen their internal audit function, making it more resilient and effective in the face of technological advancements.

To progress strategic adaptation and effectively manage risks associated with technological advancements, organizations should focus on several key areas. Investing in comprehensive training programs will ensure employees stay updated on the latest technological advancements and best practices, fostering continuous learning and professional development. Creating a flexible and agile work environment is crucial, along with implementing agile methodologies to streamline processes. Empowering and engaging employees by promoting a culture of trust and active participation in decision-making will drive proactive risk management. Cultivating a supportive organizational culture that values collaboration, innovation, and openness to change, along with recognizing and rewarding aligned behaviour, is essential. Optimizing physical workspace design to facilitate both individual and collaborative work will enhance productivity and well-being. Regular skills gap analysis and targeted training programs are necessary to address deficiencies. Fostering diversity and inclusion, encouraging innovation and creativity, and enhancing technology literacy among employees will further strengthen the workforce. Additionally, optimizing recruitment strategies to attract adaptable, innovative talent, implementing robust cybersecurity measures, and fostering continuous improvement through regular feedback are vital. Engaging stakeholders in the change process ensures their insights are considered, contributing to a resilient internal audit function capable of navigating technological advancements and organizational change.

Based on the analysis regarding the significant relationship between components of identifying risk in organizational change and internal factors influencing strategic adaptation, several recommendations can enhance organizational practices. Although the correlation between internal factors and risk identification components is weak and not statistically significant, organizations should continue to prioritize and improve specific internal factors such as leadership alignment, workplace environment, skills assessment, technological advancement, and change management. Strengthening these areas can contribute to overall organizational resilience and adaptability. Additionally, enhancing risk identification processes independently, through regular assessments, technology utilization, effective collaboration, and feedback mechanisms, is crucial. Adopting an integrated approach that aligns internal factors and risk identification components strategically can enhance organizational agility. Continuous monitoring, investing in research and development, fostering cross-functional collaboration, and benchmarking against best practices will further improve adaptability and risk management.

Future research should delve deeper into the interactions between internal factors and risk identification components to understand their combined impact on organizational adaptation and resilience. Investigating specific contexts and industries, conducting longitudinal studies, and examining the role of emerging technologies in risk management processes are essential. Comparative studies across different organizational sizes and

structures can identify tailored best practices, contributing to more effective risk management strategies.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research has been conducted with strict adherence to ethical standards to ensure the integrity and credibility.

Ensuring that all work presented is original and that any use of others' work is properly cited. Proper attribution has been given to all sources of information, including ideas, text, and data, through comprehensive citation practices. All direct quotes, paraphrased ideas, and data sourced from existing literature are accurately cited using the appropriate academic citation style. The analysis, discussions, and conclusions presented are based on the author's original research and insights. Plagiarism detection software was used to check the originality of the content to ensure that no unintentional plagiarism occurred. This step verifies that all parts of the thesis are unique and correctly attributed to their original sources.

All participants involved in this research were fully informed about the purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits of the study. Written informed consent was obtained from each participant prior to their involvement. The confidentiality of all participants has been rigorously maintained by anonymizing their data and securely storing all sensitive information. Pseudonyms and codes were used to protect participants' identities, and any identifying details have been omitted or altered to prevent disclosure. All findings reflect the true outcomes of the research conducted. Limitations and potential errors have been transparently acknowledged to provide a clear understanding of the study's scope and boundaries.

This ethical statement serves to assure that the research presented in this thesis was conducted with the highest level of ethical integrity, contributing to the advancement of knowledge in the field of risk management during organizational change.

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